

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SPECIES DIVERSITY AND PATHOGENIC FEATURES OF MICROMYCETES IN RESIDENCES

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Abstract

The presented work is dedicated to determining the status of sick buildings in residential complexes. It was determined that 52 species of micromycetes belonging to 18 genera are spread in residential buildings. It is known that micromycetes spread in the interior of residential buildings can be found in various forms such as cells, propagules, mycelial fragments, mycelial segments, etc. Therefore, the status of sick building can be applied to buildings that seriously violate mycological safety principles.

Keywords: residential complexes, micromycet, adhesion, invasion, dissemination, micotic infection, micological safety.

Although the recent rapid population growth and intensive urbanization have led to the further expansion and architectural renewal of the central settlements, on the other hand. They have also exacerbated the environmental situation. Therefore, the modern city is characterized as a special ecosystem, fundamentally different from the medical biocenoses. It should be noted that the urban ecosystem, which includes the majority of the world's population, accounts for 1,5% of the total area of the Earth [1;2]. In addition, the recent influx of people to the central cities and the increase in the number of modern residential complexes due to social problems has led to aggravation of not only the ecological but also the mycological situation. Thus, if we take into account the negative impact of the mycocomplex inside the building on human health, then it becomes clear how important it is to study these fungi. In this regard micro-organisms living inside the building are considered a risk factor for the development of a number of diseases of mycotic origin in the body and are therefore called. "The Source of disease of civilization". Although research in this area began in the 1930s, some problematic issues remain unresolved. In this regard, the study of biological ecology of micromycetes that make up the mycobiota of residential complexes is considered very relevant for the prevention, diagnosis and therapy of mycogenic sensitization [3;5;6].

Construction work is also being carried out on a large scale in Baku capital of the republic. It should be noted that the misuse of residential buildings by the residents of the building creates a real basis for the emergence of potential sources of infection in these facilities, which leads to an increase in risk factors for human health and emergence of various mycotic diseases.

The purpose of the presented work was to assess the sanitary-mycological condition in such residential

buildings as one of the main principles of mycological safety.

The object of research was registered rooms of different status in 47 apartments of 25 residential buildings built in different years in Baku, including kitchen, bathroom, caridor, living room and bedroom. The area of these apartments has varied between 5-35 m³. As the main criteria for the selection of mycological analysis, residents have long been living in the building and the observation of how many members of a family area observed 18 residential apartments are located on the IX-XII floors of the residential buildings and 18 on the III-VIII 18th floor and 18. Micological samples from residential buildings were taken from various status rooms from the atmosphere and the dust mass. Sedimentation and applications were used during the removal of samples. The patterns are decorated in Chapex, Chapk-Doks and Saburo nutritious environments. Clinical strains were used to determine the pathogenicity of studied micromycetes. For this purpose, clinical materials were obtained from the serious patients with allergis and mycosis. At the same time, the number of micromycetes was calculated based on the Omelyanski formula. Experiments were repeated 4-6 times [4;7].

25 multi – storey residential buildings constructed in different areas of Baku were studied from the mycological point of view. It was found that 52 species micromycetes of 18 genera were distributed in the residential buildings registered for the study (Table 1). As can be seen from the table, the species *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* make up half of the total mycobiota within the mycocomplex formed in residential buildings, characterized by a fairly wide range of species. *Cladosporium* and *Mucor* species each represent 15 species and account for 15,4% of mycobiota, *Acremonium*, *Alternaria*, *Rhizopus* and *Ulocladium* species

each consist of 2 species, 15,2% of mycobiota and representatives of the remaining 10 genera account for 19,2% of the total mycobiota constitute. Among the fungi have a superior position. However, in the interior of residential buildings, dark-colored fungi, opportunistic fungi, including allergens, conventional pathogens, etc are found.

It should be noted that the number of opportunistic fungi within the mycobiota formed in residential

buildings operated by humans for a long time reaches such a level that they even have the opportunity to become permanent members of the dominant nucleus. It has been established that the structural composition of the dominant core of the mycobiota formed in residential building is quite rich and consists of the following fungi: *Acremonium charticola* Gams; *Aspergillus clavatus*

Table 1.

Structural organization of mycocomplex and species diversity for malired in residential buildings

S №	Fungal genera	Fungal species
1	<i>Acremonium</i> (1/2)	<i>Acremonium Strictum</i> W.Gams; <i>A. charticola</i> Gams
2	<i>Alternaria</i> (1/2)	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> Keissl; <i>A.tenkissima</i> (Kunze: Fr) Wilt
3	<i>Aspergillus</i> (1/14)	<i>Aspergillus candidus</i> Link; <i>A.clavatus</i> Desm; <i>A.flavus</i> Link:Fr; <i>A.fumigatus</i> Fresen; <i>A.glaucus</i> Link; <i>A.niger</i> Tiegh; <i>A.nidulans</i> Winter; <i>A.sydowii</i> Church; <i>A.ochraceus</i> K.Wilh; <i>A.repens</i> Fischer; <i>A.terreus</i> Thom; <i>A.ustus</i> Bainier; <i>A.versicolor</i> (Vuill) Tirab
4	<i>Aureobasidium</i> (1/1)	<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i> (de Bary) Arnaud
5	<i>Botrytis</i> (1/1)	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i> Pers
6	<i>Chaetomium</i> (1/1)	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i> Kunze:Fr
7	<i>Cladosporium</i> (1/4)	<i>Cladosporium Cladosporioides</i> de Vries; <i>C.elatum</i> (Harz) Nannf; <i>C.herbarum</i> (Pers;Fr) Link; <i>C.sphaerospermum</i> Pens
8	<i>Mucor</i> (1/4)	<i>Mucor circinelloides</i> Tiegh; <i>M.hiemalis</i> Wehmer; <i>M.plumbeus</i> Bonard; <i>M.racemosus</i> Fresen
9	<i>Paecilomyces</i> (1/1)	<i>Paecilomyces variotii</i> Bainier
10	<i>Penicillium</i> (1/12)	<i>Penicillium Brevi-compactum</i> Dierckx; <i>P.canescens</i> Sopp; <i>P.chryogenum</i> Thom; <i>P.citrinum</i> Thom; <i>P.claviforme</i> Bainier; <i>P.funiculosum</i> Thom; <i>P.fraquentas</i> West; <i>P.decumbens</i> Thom; <i>P.purpurogenum</i> Stoll; <i>P.terlikowski</i> Zaleski; <i>P.janthinellum</i> Biourge; <i>P.verrucosum</i> Stolk et Hedlok
11	<i>Rhizomucor</i> (1/1)	<i>Rhizomucor pusillus</i> (Lindt) Schipper
12	<i>Rhizopus</i> (1/2)	<i>Rhizopus arrhizus</i> Fiseher; <i>Rh.nigricans</i> Ehrenb
13	<i>Scopulariopsis</i> (1/1)	<i>Scopulariopsis brevicaulis</i> (Abbut) Sacc
14	<i>Stachybotrys</i> (1/1)	<i>Stachybotrys artra</i> Corda
15	<i>Stemphyllium</i> (1/1)	<i>Stemphyllium botryosum</i> Wall
16	<i>Sporotrichum</i> (1/1)	<i>Sporotrichum Pruinosum</i> Gilman
17	<i>Trichoderma</i> (1/1)	<i>Trichoderma viride</i> pers
18	<i>Uliclodaium</i> (1/2)	<i>Ulocladium consortiale</i> Simmons; <i>U.chartarum</i> Simmons

Desm A. fumigatus Fresen; *Alternaria alternate* Keissl; *Cladosporium cladosporioides* de Vries, *Mucor plumbeus* Bonard; *Penicillium chrysogenum* Phom; *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis* Sacc; *Stachybotrys atra* Corda; *Ulocladium chartarum* Simmons. As can be seen, 9 genera of micromycete species participated in the structural organization of the dominant core of the mycobiota formed in the studied residential buildings. Considering that more than 60% of the dominant core consists of opportunistic fungi, then the mycological situation in such buildings is considered unsatisfactory. As a result of this, 35-40% of building residents had

allergic rhinitis, 30-35% of atopic dermatitis, 20-25% of bronchial asthma and general depression.

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